

File name: betaSweepWL

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 88 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: cdfB13WLwithInset

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 1307 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: cdfD1000WL

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 474 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: cdfD2500WL

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 170 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: cdfNoCloudInt0002WLC1to500

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 182 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: cdfNoCloudInt0002WLwithInset

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: pdf 77 KB, fig 46 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: cdfQAM16R12iwithInset

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 232 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: cdfQAM256R34

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 174 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions

on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: cdfSize5WL

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: pdf (uneditable)

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 135 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: cdfSize10WL

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 779 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: convergence2

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 106 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: delayComparison50kB_20semilogyNoLegendD

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: pdf 124 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks

With Latency Constraints,”in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: delayComparison50kBD

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: 264 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, ”Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints,”in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: Fog_offloading_corrected8

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: pdf 205 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, ”Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints,”in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: freqSweepWLAvg

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: pdf 92 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, ”Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints,”in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: freqSweepWLrej

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: pdf 82 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, ”Task Allocation for Energy

Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints,"in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: Hist2DinFogCorrectedDLongThin

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: pdf 34 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints,"in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: Hist2DRejectedCorrectedDLongThin

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: pdf 33 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints,"in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: numWireless50_2

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: pdf 110 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints,"in IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.

File name: P_beta_f

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: eps

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7961657>

Size: pdf 79 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated using: Algorithm 1 and Table II from Generated based on: chapter VI.A in B. Kopras, B. Bossy, F. Idzikowski, P. Kryszkiewicz and H. Bogucka, "Task Allocation for Energy Optimization in Fog Computing Networks With Latency Constraints,"in IEEE Transactions

on Communications, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 8229-8243, Dec. 2022.
